

Search-Based Feature Re-Modularization for Software Product Line Evolution

Supplementary Material

Introduction

This document contains the questionnaire and the video used in the qualitative study presented in the manuscript entitled “Architectural Feature Re-Modularization for Software Product Line Evolution”, submitted to the Special Issue Advances and Applications in Search-Based Software Engineering of the Automated Software Engineering Journal.

Video

The video used to contextualize the respondents can be seen by accessing the link below <https://drive.google.com/file/d/15awXgSBpDT6kjP9JGqaWXNKWeDe6OONF/view?usp=sharing>

Qualitative Analysis Questionnaire

Qualitative evaluation questionnaire on feature modularization in Software Product Line Architecture Design (PLA).

Step 01 – Evaluation of design alternatives for Arcade Game Maker (AGM)

I. Brief description of SPL Arcade Game Maker (AGM)

The product line (SPL) Arcade Game Maker (AGM) was developed by Software Engineering Institute (SEI) and produces a set of arcade games, in other words, products that have one or more games. Each game can be controlled by only one player that, partly, controls the moving objects. The main purpose is to score points hitting static obstacles. Those games have since big until small obstacles and are available on a wide variety of platforms. The main games included in the AGM are “Bowling”, “Brickles” and “Pong”.

II. AGM’s Similarities and Variabilities

II.1 Similarities

- Every game has its elements:

- Every game has a set of Sprites, which are elements in the game that the player can see and interact with;
- Every game has a set of Rules, which are the instructions that restrain the action in the game. For example, a game can have a rule that says that if a moving object crashes into a static obstacle it may obey the laws of physics;
- Every game does implicate movements;
- The elements in the game which the player interacts must be inserted inside a rectangle with a precise size, as well as it has points for the operation of the game; and,
- Every game is accessed through the main menu and has specific menus that lead to specific interfaces.

II.2 Variabilities

The game elements may or may not have a pair of elements that reacts to an action.

- Game elements, according to the game used, can present elements that do not move, as well it can present elements that move, it can even have both kinds.
- The walls can or not exist in a game;
- The moving elements in a game will always have an established speed;
- The moving elements in a game can be called puck and/or paddle;
- Types of rules: this is the major difference between the games. Some rules are related to the laws of physics (gravity, collision, etc.) and can be applied to many other games. Other rules are specifically related to a game and can be used in all implementation of this same game, but it does not apply to another games; and,
- Movement types: in some games, the movements are inherent to the game operation. It happens periodically and it is oriented by the time. In other games, the player chooses and starts the movement, being guided by the author.

III. Features

The SPL AGM has ten features, which are briefly described below:

- Play: to initiate a match and play any available game in the SPL product;
- Save: actions related to saving a match in a specific game;
- Collision: when dealing with actions related to collision of objects in the game;
- Movement: when the actions are related to movements;
- Bowling: items and rules related exclusively to the game “Bowling”;
- Brickles: items and rules related exclusively to the game “Brickles”;
- Pong: items and rules related exclusively to the game “Pong”;
- Pause: action related to pausing a match during a game in progress;
- Configuration: responsible for setting ups, such as installing;
- Logging: responsible for keeping the game’s operations log.

Notice that in our study the features are mapped into architectural elements (interface, class, methods, etc.) using UML stereotypes, that means that the architectural element which contains the stereotype contributes to the accomplishment of the feature noted in the stereotype.

Question 1. Analyze the alternatives shown below (solutions A, B and C) to an excerpt of PLA design, that contains different modularization for the features <<bowling>>, <<configuration>>, <<logging>> and <<play>>. Observe that the features are mapped in the design alternatives using the UML stereotypes, for example, <<bowling>>. In other words, it means that the architectural element (interface, class, methods, etc.) contains the stereotype required to realize the feature noted in the stereotype. It should be observed that <<bowling, play>> indicates that the bowling and play features are realized by the architectural element. The feature specification can be found in the section III of the SPL description.

Solution A

Solution B

Solution C

Examining the alternatives above, in your opinion, which is the best option for a design? Please, classify the solutions according to what you think is the best modularized option to simplify the SPL evolution.

	A	B	C
Best Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Intermediate Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Least suitable Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Question 2. Analyze the three alternatives below (solutions A, B and C) to an excerpt of PLA design that contains different modularization to the features <<configuration>>, <<play>> and <<save>>.

Solution A

Solution B

Solution C

Examining the alternatives above, in your opinion, which is the best option for a design? Please, classify the solution according to what you think is the best modularized option to simplify the SPL evolution.

	A	B	C
Best Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Intermediate Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Least suitable Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Step 02 – Evaluation of design alternatives for BET

I. Brief SPL BET description

The product line BET supports the management of urban transport. Among the available features are payment for transportation by electronic card, automatic opening of the boarding gate and payment of integration trips. The SPL BET was conceived based on three software products for Brazilian cities transportation control.

II. BET's Similarities and Variabilities

II.1 Similarities

- Basic access: corresponding to the user's access feature, in this case the passenger, to the basic information in the BET web system referring to the passengers' data and their cards, such as the expiring date and its charges.
- Staff authentication: it corresponds to the necessary authentication for the road company employees (clerks and maintainers) to use the SPL BET web system. According to the employee position, there are different types of features available in the system. The clerk can use only the parts of the system that refers to the charges and acquisition of the card.
- Types of passengers: it corresponds to the existence of categories between the passengers with specific attributes. To acquire the card, they must be associated with a specific type of passenger of the road company.
- Discount Policy: it corresponds to a feature related to the charge on the cards which receives a discount percentage for ticket purchase using a card. It happens according to the discount policy related to the type of passenger.
- Passenger: it corresponds to a feature related to the responsible for the charge of a card. The passenger must require the specific charge card to a road company clerk.

II.2 Variabilities

The variabilities SPL BET includes the possibility of additional access, passenger authentication, various integration possibilities, including bus stop integration by time, integration line, number of travels restriction with integration, traveling payments with cards, definition of card restriction for cards combination and number cards, definition of user companies and their pass limit.

III. Features

The SPL BET has 118 features. The features used in the questions 3 and 4 are briefly described below.

- BET: general actions related to SPL control;

- Basic Access: user access, in this case the passenger access, to basic information in the BET web system which refers to the consultation of passenger data and their cards, such as expiring date and charges;
- Additional Access: access to travelling information, such as trips made using the card and the definition (creation and exclusion) of travel patterns;
- Passenger Type: responsible to control the passenger type;
- Card Payment: payment rules and controls of the races made using the card;
- Discount Policy: items and rules related to the discount policy applied to the passenger type.

Notice that in our study the features are mapped by architectural elements (interface, class, methods, etc.) using UML stereotypes, in other words it means that the architectural element that has the stereotype contributes to the accomplishment of the feature noted in the stereotype.

Question 3. Analyze the alternatives below (solutions A, B and C) for an excerpt of PLA design that contains different modularization to the features <<additionalAccess>>, <<basicAccess>>, <<cardPayment>> and <<passengerType>> . Observe that the features are mapped in the design using the UML stereotypes, such as <<cardPayment>>. It means that the architectural element (interface, class, method, etc.), which has the stereotype, contributes to the accomplishment of the feature noted in the stereotype. You should notice that the stereotype <<bET, discountPolicy>> indicates that features bET and discountPayment are realized by the architectural element. The specification can be found in the section III of the SPL description.

Solution A

Solution B

Solution C

Examining the alternatives above, in your opinion, which is the best design alternative? Please, classify the solution according to what you think is the best modularized option to simplify the SPL evolution.

	A	B	C
Best Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Intermediate Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Least suitable Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Question 4. Analyze the alternatives shown below (solutions A, B and C) for an excerpt of PLA design that contains different modularization for the features <<bET>> e <<discountPolicy>>.

Solution A

Solution B

Solution C

Examining the alternatives above, in your opinion, which is the best design alternative? Please, classify the solution according to what you think is the best modularized option to simplify the SPL evolution.

	A	B	C
Best Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Intermediate Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Least suitable Solution	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Step 3 – Evaluation of Evolution Scenarios

In this stage, we aim to simulate some evolution scenarios considering the domain of the SPL BET, which involves a public transportation service using buses as the transportation method. We will propose three scenarios in which you, as a software architect, need to evolve the SPL BET to add new features.

Question 5. Imagine a smart city context in which BET will be adopted, and it needs to be evolved to support integration between buses, subway, and trains. In this scenario, it is necessary to add new types of transportation. To achieve this, the features «additionalAccess» and «passengerType» (solutions A, B, and C) are directly affected.

Which design alternative would be most appropriate to facilitate your work as a software architect in this possible evolution of the SPL? Please justify your choice.

Solution A

Solution B

Solution C

Question 6. For this scenario, it will be necessary to include new payment methods, such as digital wallets and QR code payments. The inclusion of other payment methods will affect the «cardPayment» feature and may also affect the «policyDiscount» feature (see images below). Which design alternative would be most appropriate to facilitate your work as a software architect in this potential evolution of the SPL? Please justify your choice.

Solution A

Solution B

Solution C

Question 7. In this scenario, we are interested in including automatic passenger identification using Bluetooth devices, within an Internet of Things (IoT) context. Here, the «cardPayment» and «passengerType» features may be affected.

Which of the design alternatives presented below would be most appropriate to facilitate your work as a software architect in this possible evolution of the SPL? Please justify your choice.

Solution A

Solution B

Solution C

